

SUSAAN

SUSTAINABLE ANTIMICROBIAL
AND ANTIVIRAL NANOCOATING

New Sustainable Antiviral and Antimicrobial Nanocoating for textile, plastic and metallic high traffic objects, developing Active Nano Materials (ANMs) to improve efficiency, decreasing contact time and toxicity.

SUSAAN project aims to develop antiviral and antimicrobial surfaces including development of fast active response and durable surfaces, considering ease of use, low toxicity and health issues and finally targeting a global sustainability concept, understood as environmental, economic and social sustainability for the required product and application.

42 Months

7 Countries

7 Work packages

13 Partners

Estimated Project Cost
€5,754,846.25

PROJECT PARTNERS

PROJECT IMPACT

SUSAAN will contribute not only to overcome actual problems of risk of spread of infection on pandemic period but also to create healthier living and working environment and to improve citizen health and enhance public health.

The new improved methodology and new materials could generate new actors including manufacturers, sellers and end-users, creating a huge impact on technology, economy and society.

The transition to sustainable chemicals will also be mindful of socio-economic consequences including employment impacts on specific regions, sectors and workers.

SUSAAN technology and new products development may also give rise to new market opportunities in the future, new jobs, new knowledge, and impact on the scientific area.

PROJECT COORDINATOR

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PROJECT
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